

PUBLIC POLICIES OF TAX INCENTIVES AND THE IMPACT ON BRAZILIAN HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this article is to elaborate on the quality and evolution of higher education in the context of public educational policies focused on tax incentives for private and mixed-economy education institutions, questioning whether these programs contribute to the promotion of an equitable and high-quality higher education. The overall goal was to analyze the evolutionary approach of public higher education, as well as to quantify the benefits of these policies for society, through a literature review. The results, after analyzing these educational policies, show that the program positively contributed to the evolution of higher education.

Keywords: Public Policies; Higher Education; Equitable Education; Evolution of Higher Education; Tax Incentive Policies.

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